

YOUTH VOTER ORIENTATION IN BALI IN THE 2024 PRESIDENTIAL ELECTION

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Abstract. This study aims to analyze the orientation of young voters in the 2024 Presidential Election using a cross-tabulation approach across various demographic and social variables. The research employs a quantitative methodology with Chi-square test analysis to examine relationships among variables. The sample consists of 595 respondents from Generation Z and Millennials. The results indicate that gender, occupation, and education have a significant influence on preferences for presidential and vice-presidential candidate pairs. Specifically, Candidate Pair No. 2 dominates support across nearly all categories. In contrast, age and organizational participation show no significant effect on respondents' choices. These findings suggest that the political orientation of young voters is more strongly influenced by socio-political background and educational level than by age or organizational experience.

Keywords: Young voters, 2024 Presidential Election, political orientation, cross-tabulation.

INTRODUCTION

On February 14, 2024, the Indonesian people held a five-year democratic event, namely simultaneous general elections to elect the President and Vice President (presidential election), members of the legislature (House of Representatives at national, provincial, and district/city levels), as well as members of the Regional Representative Council (DPD). The 2024 Presidential Election marks the fifth direct presidential election in Indonesia's electoral history. The first direct presidential election was conducted in 2004, based on Law Number 23 of 2003 concerning the election of the President and Vice President (Sugitanata & Majid, 2021).

Direct presidential and vice-presidential elections are considered more democratic compared to the previous system, in which they were appointed by the People's Consultative Assembly (MPR) as mandated by the 1945 Constitution prior to its amendments. Because they are elected directly by the people, the President and Vice President obtain a direct mandate and tangible support from voters. The advantages of direct elections include: (1) providing greater opportunities for the emergence of leaders aligned with the will of the majority, and (2) maintaining governmental stability by reducing the likelihood of mid-term dismissal, in line with the presidential system (Subiyanto, 2020).

The 2024 Presidential Election was contested by three candidate pairs: (1) Anies Rasyid Baswedan and Abdul Muhaimin Iskandar; (2) Prabowo Subianto and Gibran Rakabuming Raka; and (3) Ganjar Pranowo and Mahfud MD. This election is particularly noteworthy due to the candidacy of a vice-presidential candidate under the age of 40 (36 years old), namely Gibran Rakabuming Raka, the Mayor of Surakarta and the eldest son of President Joko Widodo. His eligibility is based on Constitutional

Court Decision Number 90/PUU-XXI/2023 concerning additional experience requirements related to electoral positions in the minimum age criteria for presidential and vice-presidential candidates (Constitutional Court, 2023).

The General Elections Commission (KPU) established the Final Voter List (DPT) for the 2024 election at 204,807,222 voters across 38 provinces in Indonesia (kpu.go.id, 2023). Several studies indicate that Millennials and Generation Z are expected to become the largest voter groups in the 2024 election. Young voters, defined as individuals aged 17–37 years, are projected to increase significantly. The Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS) estimates that the number of young voters in this presidential election will reach approximately 114 million, or around 52% of the total registered voters.

Young voters represent a generation with distinct characteristics, backgrounds, and challenges compared to previous generations. Generally, they come from relatively stable economic backgrounds, are well-educated, and reside in urban or peri-urban areas. They are open to new ideas, highly critical, and independent. These differences in traits, backgrounds, experiences, and challenges must be well understood, particularly in preparing young voters who are intelligent, critical, and future-oriented (Wardhani, 2018).

Research on the attitudes, behavior, and perceptions of Indonesian young voters in the 2024 election conducted by the Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS) shows that, in general, young people perceive democracy in Indonesia as functioning well. The most notable difference compared to the 2019 election lies in the desired leadership characteristics. Young voters no longer prioritize leaders perceived as simple and populist; instead, they favor leaders who emphasize honesty and anti-corruption. The two most important qualities expected of future leaders are the ability to enact change and to lead during times of crisis. Additionally, experience is also considered an influential factor in shaping their preferences (Fernandes et al., 2023).

Understanding young voters and the tools to engage them is a significant advantage, particularly with the widespread use of digital media such as social media platforms. Social media is considered an effective tool for attracting first-time voters and serving as a communication platform between candidates and the public. Campaign strategies utilizing platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and Telegram are expected to bridge communication between candidates and their potential constituents. First-time voters may choose younger or more popular candidates, or those who present youth-oriented visions.

In the electoral context, young voters exist within a spectrum between political enthusiasm and apathy. On one hand, they are highly interested in learning about elections, especially through social media. On the other hand, this enthusiasm does not always align with actual political behavior; some first-time voters, including university students, choose not to exercise their voting rights (abstain/golput). As a generation that will shape the nation's future, the orientation of young voters is critically important. Several variables may influence their voting orientation, including age, education, occupation, gender, and organizational participation.

The 2024 election is dominated by young voters. According to Media Indonesia (2023), voters aged 17–40 account for approximately 60% or around 110 million of the total registered voters in the KPU. The distribution of young voters by age group is

presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Number of Young Voters by Age Group

Age Group	Number
20 – 24 years	23,9 million
25 – 29 years	21,9 million
30-34 years	21,1 million
35 -39 years	20,9 million
40 – 44 years	21,8 million

Source: Media Indonesia (2023)

Considering that young voters dominate the electorate in the 2024 election, it can be argued that they possess substantial power and influence over election outcomes. The participation of young voters plays a crucial role in shaping Indonesia's future political direction.

Young voters are generally characterized as critical, independent, visionary, anti-status quo, and forward-thinking. They are highly adaptive to technological advancements and actively access information through social media. As such, the younger generation can be viewed as a new force in Indonesia's political dynamics. Political education for young people is therefore a logical necessity to ensure that voter participation continues to increase in each electoral cycle (Sukendar, 2017).

According to the Bali Provincial General Elections Commission (KPU Bali, 2023), the number of registered voters (DPT) in Bali as of September 2023 reached 3,269,516 individuals. Of this total, Millennials (born between 1981–1995) account for 27.59%, while Generation Z (born between 1996–2012) account for 16.55%.

This study aims to examine the orientation of young voters in Bali in the 2024 Presidential Election by considering variables such as gender, education, occupation, and organizational participation.

METHOD

The study was conducted in Bali Province. The research data consist of primary data obtained through questionnaires distributed to respondents. The collected data were then analyzed using descriptive quantitative methods and cross-tabulation. Cross-tabulation is useful for examining relationships between categorical variables, in this case, the relationship between respondents' preferred presidential candidates and the predictor variables. The hypothesis testing method used in cross-tabulation is the Chi-square test (White, 2024).

The study population consists of all young voters (aged 17–37 years) in Bali. A minimum sample of 500 respondents meeting the research criteria was selected. Sampling was conducted proportionally across the nine districts/cities in Bali. The minimum number of respondents per district/city is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Calculation of the Number of Respondents Based on the Number of Registered Voters Using Proportional Stratified Random Sampling

Regency/City	Number of Voters	Proportional Allocation	Respondents
Buleleng	611.901 people	$\frac{611.901}{3.269.516} \cdot 500 \approx 92$	92
Denpasar	495.896 people	$\frac{495.896}{3.269.516} \cdot 500 \approx 76$	76
Badung	403.326 people	$\frac{403.326}{3.269.516} \cdot 500 \approx 62$	62
Gianyar	390.424 people	$\frac{390.424}{3.269.516} \cdot 500 \approx 60$	60
Karangasem	388.854 people	$\frac{388.854}{3.269.516} \cdot 500 \approx 59$	59
Tabanan	372.372 people	$\frac{372.372}{3.269.516} \cdot 500 \approx 57$	57
Bangli	195.894 people	$\frac{195.894}{3.269.516} \cdot 500 \approx 30$	30
Klungkung	167.052 people	$\frac{167.052}{3.269.516} \cdot 500 \approx 28$	28
Jembrana	243.797 people	$\frac{243.797}{3.269.516} \cdot 500 \approx 36$	36
Total	3.269.516 people		500 people

Source: Bali Provincial General Elections Commission (KPU Bali), 2023

Considering the relatively wide scope of the study area, the distribution of questionnaires was conducted using the snowball sampling technique. Snowball sampling is a sampling method in which researchers begin with a small number of initial respondents, who then recruit additional respondents that meet the research criteria. This process continues progressively, similar to a snowball that grows larger as it rolls.

The use of snowball sampling facilitates the identification of respondents who meet the study criteria. In addition, respondents tend to be more open, as the questionnaires are distributed through individuals they know (Ting et al., 2025).

Research Variables

The response variable (Y) in this study is the selected presidential and vice-presidential candidate pair chosen by the respondents, while the predictor variables (Xi) are presented in Table 2 below:

Table 2. Research Variables

Variable	Category	Measurement Scale
Response Variable		
Selected presidential vice presidential candidate pair (Y)	Candidate Pair No. 1 Candidate Pair No. 2 Candidate Pair No. 3 Abstention (Golput)	Nominal
Predictor Variables		
Respondent's Gender (X ₁)	0 = Female 1 = Male	Nominal
Age Category of Respondents (X ₂)	1 = Millennial 2 = Generation Z	Ordinal
Respondent's Education (X ₃)	1 ≤ Junior High School 2 = Senior High School or equivalent 3 = Higher Education	Ordinal
Respondent's Occupation (X ₄)	0 = Student 1 = Civil Servant (ASN) 2 = Others	Nominal
Organizational Participation (X ₅)	0 = Yes 1 = No	Nominal

Source: Processed data (2025)

Respondents were not only required to answer questions related to the response variable and explanatory variables, but were also given an open-ended question regarding how they obtained information about the presidential and vice-presidential candidates they intended to choose.

The stages of analysis were conducted as follows:

- Describing the distribution of votes for each presidential–vice-presidential candidate pair across regencies/cities.
- Analyzing the relationship between each predictor variable and the selected candidate pair by constructing cross-tabulations between predictor variables and the chosen candidates.
- To determine which variables have a statistically significant relationship with the selected candidate pair, the Chi-square test was employed with the following hypotheses:

H₀: There is no relationship between the predictor variables and the selected presidential vice presidential candidates.

H₁: There is a relationship between the predictor variables and the selected presidential vice presidential candidates.

The test statistics used are as follows:
$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{j=1}^k \frac{(O_{ij} - E_{ij})^2}{E_{ij}}$$

O_{ij} represents the observed frequency in row i and column j of the contingency table

E_{ij} represents the expected frequency in row i and column j of the contingency table

The degrees of freedom are calculated as $= (k - 1) (r - 1)$

The null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected if the p -value $\leq \alpha$ or if the calculated Chi-square value (χ^2) exceeds the critical Chi-square value from the table. In this study, the significance level (α) used is 0.05.

If H_0 is rejected, the direction of the differences is further examined using standardized residual analysis. According to Agresti (2027) and Field (2013), residual values $\geq |2|$ can be interpreted as cells that significantly deviate from the expected values.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Distribution of Presidential–Vice Presidential Candidate Preferences by Regency

Based on the distribution of questionnaires across all regencies/cities in Bali, a total of 595 respondents were obtained, exceeding the minimum research target of 500 respondents. The distribution of respondents' preferences for presidential–vice-presidential candidates is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Distribution of Respondents' Candidate Preferences by Regency/City in Bali

Candidate	Badung	Ban glis	Bulele ng	Giany ar	Jembra na	Karangas em	Klungku ng	Taban an	Denpa sar	Total
Candidate No. 1	4	0	12	0	4	3	1	1	2	27
Candidate No. 2	65	22	50	36	33	32	19	15	54	326
Candidate No. 3	13	8	28	22	9	16	4	53	28	181
Abstention (Golput)	9	1	9	7	4	10	6	3	12	61
Total	91	31	99	65	50	61	30	72	96	595

Source: Processed data (2025)

The questionnaire distributed to respondents not only included questions regarding their chosen presidential–vice-presidential candidates and personal characteristics, but also contained open-ended questions concerning the reasons for their choices and the sources from which they obtained information about the candidates.

Approximately 98% of respondents reported that they became familiar with the candidates through social media, particularly TikTok and YouTube, while the remainder obtained information from television broadcasts and billboards. This finding indicates that social media campaigns are highly effective in attracting voters, especially young voters who are closely attached to digital devices.

Table 3 shows that young voters in Bali demonstrate a strong preference for Candidate Pair No. 2 (Prabowo Subianto – Gibran Rakabuming Raka) compared to other candidates. This pair dominates support across nearly all regencies/cities in Bali,

with the exception of Tabanan, where Candidate Pair No. 3 (Ganjar Pranowo – Mahfud MD) is more favored.

The most frequently cited reasons for choosing Candidate Pair No. 2 include Prabowo's background as a former military officer, which is associated with firmness and strong leadership, as well as the clarity of their vision and mission. Additionally, respondents expressed interest in Gibran's figure as the son of the incumbent president, which is perceived as ensuring the continuation of existing government programs. Although some respondents mentioned informal reasons such as the "gemoy" campaign image, overall preferences were largely influenced by the "Jokowi effect" and perceptions of Prabowo as a decisive leader.

According to Subanda (2024), the figures of Prabowo, Gibran, and Joko Widodo possess strong appeal, with Jokowi perceived as pro-change and Gibran as a young leader well accepted by millennial voters. As Jokowi's son, Gibran's candidacy alongside Prabowo creates the perception of continuity in development and stability. The primary source of information influencing respondents' choices is social media, where campaign content from the Prabowo–Gibran pair on platforms such as TikTok, Instagram, and YouTube has been more intensive and widely circulated compared to other candidates, effectively resonating with young voters in Bali. Furthermore, their strong performance in various survey institutions has also influenced voter orientation.

Candidate Pair No. 3 (Ganjar Pranowo – Mahfud MD) ranks second in respondents' preferences. Respondents cited Ganjar's experience as a two-term governor of Central Java and former member of the House of Representatives, as well as Mahfud MD's reputation as a firm former Chief Justice of the Constitutional Court, as key reasons for their choice. The clarity of their vision and mission also contributes to their appeal.

Although Bali is often regarded as a stronghold of a particular political party, this does not automatically translate into support for Candidate Pair No. 3 among young voters. This phenomenon reflects a shift toward more rational voting behavior, where voters no longer automatically support candidates from a specific party. Additionally, emerging negative sentiments toward party leadership have influenced voter preferences (Subanda, 2024).

An interesting finding from Table 3 is that approximately 10% of respondents indicated their intention to abstain (golput) in the 2024 election—exceeding the number of respondents who intend to vote for Candidate Pair No. 1 (Anies Baswedan – Muhaimin Iskandar). This apathy stems from perceptions that any elected leader would not bring meaningful change, with persistent issues such as high commodity prices and widespread corruption.

According to Rahma and Fauzi (2024), abstention is a recurring phenomenon in Indonesian elections, driven by various factors, including political apathy, dissatisfaction with election outcomes, lack of confidence in candidates, and distrust in political processes.

In Bali, the popularity of Candidate Pair No. 1 is significantly lower compared to the other candidates. Out of 595 respondents, only 27 indicated support for this pair. Notably, in Bangli and Gianyar, no respondents expressed an intention to vote for Candidate Pair No. 1, while in Buleleng, 12 respondents indicated such preference.

This may be related to the demographic composition of Buleleng, which includes a higher proportion of Muslim residents.

Respondents who chose Candidate Pair No. 1 cited reasons such as Anies Baswedan’s perceived success as Governor of Jakarta, his promise of change, and his religious image. However, despite promoting a platform of change, this pair appears less appealing to young voters in Bali. This outcome reflects a fundamental mismatch between the political image of the candidate pair and the characteristics of voters in Bali, where the majority of the population adheres to Hinduism. Anies Baswedan is often associated with political support from conservative Islamic groups, creating a perceived distance from the majority of voters in Bali, who tend to be cautious about identity-based politics.

Relationship Between Respondents’ Gender and Selected Presidential–Vice-Presidential Candidates

Cross-tabulation analysis was conducted to examine whether there are significant differences in respondents’ gender with respect to their choice of presidential vice presidential candidates.

The hypotheses used are as follows:

H₀: There is no relationship between respondents’ gender and the selected presidential vice-presidential candidates.

H₁: There is a relationship between respondents’ gender and the selected presidential vice-presidential candidates.

Table 4. Cross-Tabulation of Gender and Candidate Preference

Candidate	Gender	Count	Expected Count	Adjusted Residual
Candidate No. 1	Male	11	12.2	-0.3
	Female	16	14.8	0.3
	Total	27	27.0	—
Candidate No. 2	Male	119	147.4	-2.3
	Female	207	178.6	2.1
	Total	326	326.0	—
Candidate No. 3	Male	104	81.8	2.5
	Female	77	99.2	-2.2
	Total	181	181.0	—
Abstention (Golput)	Male	35	27.6	1.4
	Female	26	33.4	-1.3
	Total	61	61.0	—
Total	Male	269	269.0	—
	Female	326	326.0	—
Grand Total		595	595.0	—

Source: Processed data (2025)

The Chi-square test results yielded a p-value of $0.00 < 0.05$, indicating that H₀ is rejected. Thus, it can be concluded that gender has a statistically significant effect on the choice of presidential vice presidential candidates in the 2024 Presidential

Election.

Table 4 shows that for male respondents, the standardized residual for Candidate Pair No. 2 is -2.3, while for Candidate Pair No. 3 it is 2.5. This indicates that male voters tend to favor Candidate Pair No. 3 and are less supportive of Candidate Pair No. 2.

For female respondents, the standardized residual for Candidate Pair No. 2 is 2.1, while for Candidate Pair No. 3 it is -2.3. These results suggest that female respondents show stronger support for Candidate Pair No. 2 compared to Candidate Pair No. 3.

Relationship Between Respondents' Occupation and Selected Presidential–Vice-Presidential Candidates

The hypotheses used are as follows:

H₀: There is no relationship between respondents' occupation and the selected presidential vice presidential candidates.

H₁: There is a relationship between respondents' occupation and the selected presidential vice presidential candidates.

The cross-tabulation between respondents' occupation and candidate preference is presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Cross-Tabulation of Respondents' Occupation and Candidate Preference

Candidate	Occupation	Count	Expected Count	Adjusted Residual
Candidate No. 1	Student	13	12.3	0.2
	Civil Servant (ASN)	4	3.1	0.5
	Others	10	11.6	-0.5
	Total	27	27.0	—
Candidate No. 2	Student	175	149.0	2.1
	Civil Servant (ASN)	28	37.3	-1.5
	Others	123	139.7	-1.4
	Total	326	326.0	—
Candidate No. 3	Student	55	82.7	-3.0
	Civil Servant (ASN)	25	20.7	0.9
	Others	101	77.6	2.7
	Total	181	181.0	—
Abstention (Golput)	Student	29	27.9	0.2
	Civil Servant (ASN)	11	7.0	1.5
	Others	21	26.1	-1.0
	Total	61	61.0	—
Total	Student	272	272.0	—
	Civil Servant (ASN)	68	68.0	—
	Others	255	255.0	—
	Grand Total	595	595.0	—

Source: Processed data (2025)

The Chi-square test results yielded a p-value of 0.000 < 0.05, indicating a

significant relationship between respondents' occupation and their choice of presidential vice presidential candidates.

Based on the adjusted residual values, students tend to prefer Candidate Pair No. 2 over Candidate Pair No. 3. Meanwhile, other occupational categories do not show a statistically significant influence on candidate preference.

Students are more frequently exposed to social media platforms such as TikTok and Instagram, where Candidate Pair No. 2 has been intensively promoted through the so-called "gemoy" campaign strategy. This finding is consistent with the argument of Muhamad Faisal (cited in Wahyudi, 2024), which suggests that Generation Z's choices are influenced by priming, namely the most memorable or salient impressions they have of a candidate. This priming effect is strongly shaped by peer influence, making the "gemoy" strategy particularly effective and memorable among Gen Z voters.

Relationship Between Respondents' Education Level and Selected Presidential-Vice-Presidential Candidates

The hypotheses used are as follows:

H₀: There is no relationship between respondents' education level and the selected presidential vice presidential candidates.

H₁: There is a relationship between respondents' education level and the selected presidential vice presidential candidates.

The cross-tabulation between respondents' education level and candidate preference is presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Cross-Tabulation of Respondents' Education Level and Candidate Preference

Candidate	Education Level	Count	Expected Count	Adjusted Residual
Candidate No. 1	Junior High School	0	0.6	-0.9
	Senior High School or equivalent	9	12.3	-1.3
	Higher Education	18	14.1	1.6
	Total	27	27.0	—
Candidate No. 2	Junior High School	5	7.7	-2.3
	Senior High School or equivalent	155	147.9	1.3
	Higher Education	166	170.4	-0.5
	Total	326	326.0	—
Candidate No. 3	Junior High School	7	4.3	1.3
	Senior High School or equivalent	87	82.1	0.9
	Higher Education	87	94.6	-1.4
	Total	181	181.0	—

Candidate	Education Level	Count	Expected Count	Adjusted Residual
Abstention (Golput)	Junior High School	2	1.4	2.5
	Senior High School or equivalent	19	27.7	-2.6
	Higher Education	40	31.9	1.7
	Total	61	61.0	—
Total	Junior High School	14	14.0	—
	Senior High School or equivalent	270	270.0	—
	Higher Education	311	311.0	—
	Grand Total	595	595.0	—

Source: Processed data (2025)

The Chi-square test yielded a p-value of $0.007 < 0.05$, indicating that respondents' education level has a statistically significant influence on their choice of presidential–vice-presidential candidates.

Based on the adjusted residual values in Table 6, support for Candidate Pair No. 1 is relatively low and not prominent across any education level. Candidate Pair No. 2 demonstrates strong support across all levels of education, with particularly higher support among respondents with a senior high school education. Meanwhile, Candidate Pair No. 3 tends to be preferred by respondents with a junior high school education and is less favored by those with higher education backgrounds.

These findings are consistent with voter behavior theory, which suggests that education level influences voter orientation. Higher levels of education are associated with more rational political participation, rather than decisions driven solely by emotional factors or party/group identity (Borgonovi et al., 2010; Glaeser et al., 2007).

According to Br Ginting and Ivanna (2024), in their study of university students, although educational attainment influences voting preferences in the 2024 presidential election, other factors such as social status, social media exposure, and individual well-being also play important roles.

Relationship Between Respondents' Age Category and Selected Presidential–Vice-Presidential Candidates

The hypotheses used are as follows:

H_0 : There is no relationship between respondents' age category and the selected presidential vice presidential candidates.

H_1 : There is a relationship between respondents' age category and the selected presidential vice presidential candidates.

The cross-tabulation between respondents' age category and candidate preference is presented in Table 7.

Table 7. Cross-Tabulation of Respondents' Age Category and Candidate Preference

Candidate	Age Category	Count	Expected Count	Adjusted Residual
Candidate No. 1	Millennial	26	23.9	0.4
	Generation Z	1	3.1	-1.2
	Total	27	27.0	—
Candidate No. 2	Millennial	280	288.2	-0.5
	Generation Z	46	37.8	1.3
	Total	326	326.0	—
Candidate No. 3	Millennial	165	160.0	0.4
	Generation Z	16	21.0	-1.1
	Total	181	181.0	—
Abstention (Golput)	Millennial	55	53.9	0.1
	Generation Z	6	7.1	-0.4
	Total	61	61.0	—
Total	Millennial	526	526.0	—
	Generation Z	69	69.0	—
	Grand Total	595	595.0	—

Source: Processed data (2025)

The Chi-square test yielded a p-value of 0.159, indicating that there is no statistically significant difference between Generation Z and Millennials in determining their preferred presidential vice presidential candidates.

Both Millennials and Generation Z are digital-native generations characterized as adaptive, creative, critical, and socially aware. Their active engagement with social media platforms contributes to the absence of significant differences in their voting preferences.

Relationship Between Respondents' Organizational Participation and Selected Presidential–Vice-Presidential Candidates

Table 8. Cross-Tabulation of Organizational Participation and Candidate Preference

Candidate	Organizational Participation	Count	Expected Count	Adjusted Residual
Candidate No. 1	Active	18	19.0	-0.2
	Not Active	9	8.0	0.3
	Total	27	27.0	—
Candidate No. 2	Active	234	229.0	0.3
	Not Active	92	97.0	-0.5
	Total	326	326.0	—
Candidate No. 3	Active	129	127.2	0.2
	Not Active	52	53.8	-0.3

Candidate	Organizational Participation	Count	Expected Count	Adjusted Residual
	Total	181	181.0	
Abstention (Golput)	Active	37	42.9	-0.9
	Not Active	24	18.1	1.4
	Total	61	61.0	
Total	Active	418	418.0	
	Not Active	177	177.0	
	Grand Total	595	595.0	

Source: Processed data (2025)

The Chi-square value of 0.347 indicates that organizational participation does not have a statistically significant effect on young voters in determining their choices. As is well known, Millennials and Generation Z are more active on social media; therefore, most of the information they receive is obtained through these platforms rather than through organizational involvement.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of cross-tabulation analysis of 595 young voter respondents, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. There is a significant relationship between gender, occupation, and education level and the choice of presidential–vice-presidential candidate pairs.
2. Male voters tend to show higher support for Candidate No. 3 beyond expected values, while female voters show significant support for Candidate No. 2.
3. The student group demonstrates strong support for Candidate No. 2, while respondents in the “other occupations” category tend to prefer Candidate No. 3.
4. Education level significantly influences political preferences. Voters with a junior high school background show a higher tendency toward abstention (golput) compared to other education groups.
5. Organizational participation and age category do not have a significant effect on the voting patterns of young voters in the 2024 presidential election.

Overall, Candidate No. 2 emerges as the candidate with the highest level of support across nearly all segments of young voters in this study.

For Political Practitioners and Campaign Teams:

Given the significant relationship between gender, occupation, and education level with candidate preference, campaign teams are advised to implement more targeted segmentation strategies. Special attention should be given to female voters and student groups, as these segments demonstrate strong and distinct support patterns for certain candidates.

For Election Organizers (KPU/Bawaslu):

The findings indicate a higher-than-expected level of abstention among young voters with lower educational backgrounds (junior high school level). Therefore, it is recommended that election socialization programs be more intensively directed

toward lower-education groups to reduce abstention rates and increase political participation among young voters who have limited access to formal information channels.

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